

Crop and resource management

Integrated fertilizer management

Effect of granular N fertilizers on growth and grain yield of rice

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We studied the effect of granular N fertilizers on the growth, grain yield, and nutrient use efficiency of rice under irrigated conditions during the 1991 dry season (DS) at the DRR Experimental Farm. Soil is a Vertisol with pH 8.3, CEC 49.2 meq/100 g soil, 0.01% total N (modified Kjeldahl method), and 6 ppm available P (Olsen's method). The experimental plots, except control, were fertilized uniformly with 90-26.4-41.5 kg NPK/ha.

Fertilizers studied were prilled urea (PU) of 350-400 prills/g wt, large granule urea (LGU) of 4-6 granules/g wt, urea supergranules (USG) of 1 g wt each, diammonium phosphate (DAP) of 28-32 granules/g wt, large granule diammonium phosphate (LDAP) of 7-10 granules/g wt, and single super-

Grain yield and nutrient response as influenced by granular fertilizers, 1991-92 dry season (rabi).

Treatment ¹	Grain yield (t/ha)	N response (kg grain/kg N)	Nutrient response (kg grain/kg nutrient)
Control	2.9	-	-
PU + SSP	4.8	20.8	9.3
PU + DAP	5.2	25.2	11.3
PU + LDAP	5.6	30.5	12.7
LGU + SSP	5.2	26.3	11.9
LGU + DAP	5.1	24.9	11.2
LGU + LDAP	5.5	28.8	13.0
USG + SSP	6.1	35.7	16.0
USG + LDAP	6.4	39.0	17.6
LSD (0.05)	0.4		
CV (%)	5.7		

¹All treatments, except control, received 90 kg N/ha, 26.4 kg P/ha, and 33.2 kg K/ha.

phosphate (SSP) (see table). DAP, LDAP, and SSP were applied basally; PU and LGU in two splits; and USG was placed in the root zone 7 d after transplanting.

Large granular treatments (USG + LDAP) had significant increases in growth and grain yield and were superior to all other treatments except USG + SSP. We observed promising results in all treatments with LDAP, irrespective of N source. Grain yields with LDAP

treatments were 5.5-6.4 t/ha, compared with 4.8-6.1 t/ha with SSP treatments.

The response of grain yield to N and also the unit response per kg of NPK was high in treatments receiving point placement of N as USG and basal dose of LDAP.

It can be inferred that rice responds better to granular N and P fertilizers than to PU and SSP. Placement of N as USG in the root zone and basal application of P and part of the N as LDAP gave the best results for growth, yield performance, and nutrient use efficiency in rice under DS irrigated conditions. ■

Fertilizer management—inorganic sources

Modern varieties (MVs) yield more than traditional varieties (TVs) in Cambodia regardless of fertilizer use

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Modern varieties and associated technologies were evaluated in a series of on-farm adaptive trials (OFAT) initiated by CIRP in 1990. Farmers conducted the trials using their own resources and style of crop management. They did not receive inputs or insurance against crop failure to ensure that test varieties were exposed to the same constraints they would encounter when adopted by farmers. Some farmers did not apply fertilizer or manure because the inputs were unaffordable or unavailable. Those using fertilizers applied a maximum of 60 kg N/ha and 30 kg P/ha.

Farmers were provided with 1 kg seed each of IR66, IR72, and Kru (IR13429-150-3-2-1), which had been identified as superior early rice varieties. Each farmer provided 1 kg seed of the best local short-duration variety to serve as a check.

Checks represented most of the common

Yield of IR66, IR72, and Kru compared with local checks in OFAT in 1990 WS (51 locations), 1991 DS (39 locations), 1991 WS (90 locations), and 1992 DS (80 locations).

Variety	With fertilizer		Without fertilizer	
	Yield (t/ha)	% over check	Yield (t/ha)	% over check
1990 WS				
23 locations				
IR66	3.3	14	2.5	0
IR72	3.1	7	2.5	0
Kru	2.9	0	3.0	17
Check	2.9	0	2.5	0
1991 DS				
22 locations				
IR66	5.4	26	3.6	3
IR72	4.9	14	3.6	3
Kru	4.8	12	3.6	3
Check	4.3	0	3.5	0
1991 WS				
60 locations				
IR66	3.1	11	3.1	15
IR72	3.0	7	3.2	19
Kru	3.1	11	3.1	15
Check	2.8	0	2.7	0
1992 DS				
36 locations				
IR66	5.1	24	4.3	13
IR72	4.7	15	3.9	3
Kru	4.8	17	4.1	8
Check	4.1	0	3.8	0